

The Biggest IT Outage in History¹

The Unintended Consequences of CrowdStrike's Content Update

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Executive Summary:

On July 19, 2024, a faulty software content update from CrowdStrike caused "the biggest IT outage in history," (Hunt, 2024) affecting numerous organizations worldwide. This incident highlights the risks of single points of failure in widely adopted cybersecurity tools. The article examines the nature of software content updates, provides examples of past update-related issues, and discusses the concept of single points of failure. Key lessons include the need for system redundancy, rigorous update testing, phased rollouts, and comprehensive incident response planning. *A comprehensive Glossary is provided at the end of this paper.*

Introduction

CrowdStrike Holdings, Inc. is an American cybersecurity company headquartered in Austin, Texas.³ On July 19, 2024, a defective Software Content Update from CrowdStrike for Windows users, caused a major global IT outage, described as "the biggest IT outage in history." The event affected organisations globally and was reported early on 19 July in Australia. Here is a sample timeline from the USA.

Date/Time (ET)	Event
July 18, Late night	911 centres and transportation services start experiencing disruptions
July 19, 2-3 AM	Major airlines (Delta, American, United, Allegiant) ground flights
July 19, 5-6 AM	Public transit systems in Northeast US report impacts
July 19, 5:30 AM	CrowdStrike acknowledges reports of crashes in its software
July 19, 6-7 AM	White House investigates; global banks report issues
July 19, 8-9 AM	Some flights resume; airports brace for busy day
July 19, 9 AM - 12 PM	Federal agencies involved; Biden briefed; 911 services start recovering
July 19, 11 AM	CrowdStrike CEO announces issue identified and fix deployed
July 19, Late morning - early afternoon	Healthcare systems and DMV operations report impacts
July 19, 4 PM	Blood centers report disruptions in operations
July 20, Morning	Microsoft est 8.5m Windows devices affected; flight disruptions cont

Table 1: CrowdStrike Event USA Timeline (Source CNN, Adapted) ⁴

The incident reportedly stemmed from a faulty update to CrowdStrike's widely adopted "Falcon Sensor" cybersecurity tool. This software has privileged access to many computer systems. Combined with its extensive adoption (driven by cybersecurity checklists and business requirements) this created a single point of failure (SPOF) across numerous organizations worldwide.^{5 6} More on SPOFs shortly.

Figure 1: The dreaded "Blue Screen of Death" was everywhere!

The outage led to unprecedented disruptions across multiple sectors, including aviation, banking, healthcare (including the NHS), transportation, and media. Many Windows PCs crashed, displaying the "blue screen of death," (above) while organizations struggled with old, manual operations if they could.

Resolving the issue often requires manual intervention on each affected machine. But the impact primarily impacted computers running Windows. Mac and Linux hosts are not affected. The event was also not classified as a cyberattack.⁷

While the full economic impact is yet to be quantified, it is expected to be substantial. This event serves as a cautionary tale, prompting organizations to reconsider their approach to cybersecurity and emphasizing the importance of system redundancy. The CrowdStrike incident was caused by a faulty software content update. To understand how this happened, let's examine what software content updates are and why they can be vulnerable.

Research Question: *How can organizations effectively balance the benefits of centralized cybersecurity solutions against the risks of creating single points of failure in critical IT infrastructure?*

What is a Software Content Update?

A software content update typically refers to new or revised digital content that is added to an existing software application or platform.

These content updates are therefore different from the software updates that change the core software or fix bugs. These software content updates focus on expanding or refreshing the functionality or user experience. In a simpler example, a mobile game might release a content update that adds new levels, characters, or storylines without changing how the game fundamentally works. A news app might push content updates throughout the day to keep its information current.

Type of Update	Description
New features or functionality	Adds new capabilities to the software incl cybersecurity
Additional levels (in games)	Expands gameplay content
New media files	Adds images, videos, or audio
Updated text or information	Refreshes existing content
New items or characters	Adds new elements to games or apps

Table 2: Types of Updates

In CrowdStrike's case, the content update likely included new threat definitions or rules for their Falcon Sensor tool. While intended to improve security, the faulty update instead caused widespread system failures. George Kurtz, CEO and founder of CrowdStrike, has appeared in several interviews and issued various statements reassuring stakeholders that the problems are being rolled back.

He however admits that this may take some time.⁸ The CrowdStrike case is unique in its scale and impact due to the critical nature of the software and its widespread adoption, but it is not totally unique. Let's look at some other examples from recent history.

Content Update Vulnerabilities

There have been several other past instances where software content updates have caused less widespread malfunctions or crashes than the CrowdStrike Incident. Here are some examples:

- **iOS 8.0.1 update (2014):** Apple released this update which caused widespread issues, including loss of cellular service and Touch ID functionality on iPhone 6 and 6 Plus devices. Apple had to quickly pull the update and release a fix.⁹
- **Windows 10 October 2018 Update:** This major content update for Windows 10 had to be paused shortly after release, due to reports of user files being deleted. Microsoft withdrew the update and re-released it about a month later after fixing the issue.¹⁰
- **Yosemite OS X Wi-Fi issues (2014):** After this major update to Apple's desktop operating system, many users reported Wi-Fi connectivity problems.¹¹

Users of **Pokemon GO**, **Facebook**, **Snapchat**, and **Adobe Creative Cloud**, have also reported post-update issues from time-to-time. These examples demonstrate that even major software companies can sometimes release updates that cause unexpected issues. It's worth noting though, that these are relatively rare compared to the vast number of successful updates. In CrowdStrike's case, we could also say that the company had become so influential in cybersecurity as to become a SPOF.

Single Points of Failure SPOFs

A single point of failure (SPOF) in IT and Telecommunications terms, refers to a component or part of a system which, if it fails, will cause the entire system to fail or significantly impair its functionality. A SPOF is therefore critical to system operation. The term itself implies that there is likely no redundancy or backup in place, and with that comes the potential to cause widespread system disruption. Common examples of SPOFs in IT and telecommunications are:

SPOF Example	Potential Impact
Single power supply for a server	Server downtime if power supply fails
Single network switch	Network outage for connected servers
Single internet connection	Loss of internet access for the entire business
Single database server	Data access issues for dependent applications
Single cooling system for a data centre	Overheating risk for all servers in the data centre

Table 3: Common Examples of Single Points of Failure (SPOFs)

Note the use of the word “single” here. A SPOF consequently increases potential organisational risks, such as system downtime, data loss, financial loss, and damage to reputation. SPOF vulnerabilities can cause other breaches of service level agreements (SLAS) and even regulatory sanctions.

For example, responsibilities for a loss of personal data due to the software update, could fall under the General Data Protection Regulation (EU GDPR), the UK Data Protection Act 2018 (DPA 2018), and (in the USA) the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA) etc. This is not thought to be a factor in the event here. Identifying and eliminating SPOFs is nevertheless a crucial part of good system design and operations, a key consideration in creating robust, highly available systems

Mitigation strategies against SPOFs can include **adding backup components** or systems (redundancy), **distributing traffic** across multiple components (load balancing), **automatic switching** to a standby system (failover systems), regular **maintenance and monitoring**, and **disaster recovery planning**. Decisions and solution will be tailored to your organisation, and a conversation with your IT and data management colleagues, and you can also reach out to us a digivertex [dot] ltd.

It can be costly to eliminate all SPOFs, some of which may be difficult to identify or address due to technical or budgetary constraints.¹² But we have now had a serious wakeup call, which needs to be heard loud and clear. There are likely to be several intense investigations into this global CrowdStrike event but before we close, perhaps we can draw a few conclusions from what we have read here.

Conclusions - Lessons Learned?

Lessons from the CrowdStrike Incident

The CrowdStrike incident of July 19, 2024, highlights significant lessons for all organizational leaders in managing IT infrastructure, software deployments and data management.

The Dangers of Single Points of Failure (SPOFs)

This event underscores the dangers of single points of failure (SPOFs) in widely adopted tools. It emphasizes the need for system redundancy and diversification of critical software and services.

Balancing Cybersecurity and Risk Management

While cybersecurity remains vital, organizations must carefully evaluate the risks associated with global reliance on any single cybersecurity tool (or vendor), especially for mission-critical systems.

There is a contrary argument that multiple sources of cybersecurity tools can also multiply the risks. But continuously evaluating vulnerabilities and SPOFs is always essential in IT infrastructure and data management, for preventing (or curtailing) such incidents.

The Importance of Rigorous Update Testing

Furthermore, as we have seen, even major companies can release updates that cause significant issues, necessitating rigorous testing of all updates, including software content updates, before such widespread deployment.

Strategies for Minimizing Update-Related Risks

- Phased Rollouts
- Quick Rollback Procedures
- Rapid Detection and Response Systems

Implementing a phased rollout of updates and maintaining quick rollback procedures are other crucial strategies we have mentioned for helping minimize potential damage. Implementing systems for rapid detection and response to software issues can also significantly reduce the impact of such problems.

The Role of Manual Processes and Offline Capabilities

Even in this "automated era," having risk-assessed manual processes, or offline capabilities, is still an important strategy for maintaining critical operations in case of such widespread IT failures.

Developing a Comprehensive Incident Response Plan

Finally, a well-prepared and rehearsed incident response plan is vital for quick and effective reactions to any such major IT disruption.

A Holistic Approach to IT Infrastructure and Risk Management

The insights outlined in this paper, collectively emphasize the importance of a comprehensive, thoughtful approach to IT infrastructure, software deployment, and risk management in our increasingly interconnected digital landscape. Together, these factors can help organizations effectively balance the benefits of centralized cybersecurity solutions against the risks of creating single points of failure in critical IT infrastructure.

Addressing Our Initial Research Question,

How can organizations effectively balance the benefits of centralized cybersecurity solutions against the risks of creating single points of failure in critical IT infrastructure?

The CrowdStrike incident clearly demonstrates that while centralized cybersecurity solutions offer significant benefits in terms of efficiency, standardization, and ease of management, they can also introduce the increased risk of creating a single point of failure (SPOF) across multiple organizations. To effectively balance these factors, organizations should consider the following approach:

1. **Hybrid Security Model:** Implement a hybrid model that combines the strengths of centralized solutions with decentralized elements. This could involve using a primary cybersecurity tool while maintaining secondary systems from different vendors as a backup. This will require careful planning.
2. **Regular Risk Assessments:** Continuously evaluate the trade-offs between centralization and diversification in your cybersecurity strategy. This should include assessing the potential impact of a failure in any (and every) single component of your security infrastructure.
3. **Segmentation and Isolation:** Implement network segmentation and isolation techniques to limit the potential spread of issues from a SPOF.
4. **Vendor Due Diligence:** When selecting centralized solutions, thoroughly assess vendors' redundancy measures, update processes, and incident response capabilities. Include essential elements of this in the SLA.
5. **Customized Deployment:** Tailor the implementation of centralized solutions to your organization's specific needs and risk profile, rather than adopting a one-size-fits-all approach.

By adopting these strategies, organizations can harness the benefits of centralized cybersecurity solutions while mitigating the risks associated with creating single points of failure. The key lies in maintaining a dynamic, risk-aware approach that continuously adapts to the evolving threat landscape and organizational needs.

Stay aware! The July 2024 CrowdStrike incident may not be the last such event.

Glossary

Blue Screen of Death: A colloquial term for the error screen displayed on Windows operating systems when a fatal system error occurs.

Content Update Vulnerabilities: Potential weaknesses or issues introduced by software content updates.

Critical Infrastructure: Systems and assets, whether physical or virtual, so vital that their incapacitation or destruction would have a debilitating impact on security, national economic security, national public health or safety, or any combination of those matters.

Cybersecurity Checklists: Standardized lists of security measures or best practices used to assess and improve an organization's cybersecurity posture.

Cybersecurity: The practice of protecting systems, networks, and programs from digital attacks.

Disaster Recovery Planning: The process of creating a system of prevention and recovery from potential threats to a company's IT infrastructure.

Failover Systems: Backup systems that automatically take over when the primary system fails.

Falcon Sensor: CrowdStrike's cybersecurity tool that detects and blocks hacking threats.

Incident Response Plan: A set of instructions to help IT staff detect, respond to, and recover from network security incidents.

IT Infrastructure: The composite hardware, software, network resources, and services required for the existence, operation, and management of an enterprise IT environment.

IT Outage: A period of time when IT systems are unavailable or not functioning correctly.

Load Balancing: The process of distributing network traffic across multiple servers to ensure no single server bears too much demand.

Manual Processes: Operations carried out by human effort rather than automated systems.

Offline Capabilities: The ability of a system or application to function without an internet connection.

Phased Rollout: A strategy for gradually implementing updates or changes across a system to minimize potential widespread issues.

Privileged Access: Higher-level access rights granted to users who need to perform administrative or sensitive functions.

Redundancy: The inclusion of extra components that can perform the same task to increase system reliability.

Risk Management: The identification, evaluation, and prioritization of risks followed by coordinated application of resources to minimize, monitor, and control the probability or actual impact of unfortunate events.

Rollback Procedures: Methods to revert a system to a previous state, often used when updates cause unexpected problems.

Service Level Agreements (SLAs): Contracts between service providers and clients that define the level of service expected from the provider.

Single Point of Failure (SPOF): A component of a system which, if it fails, will cause the entire system to fail or significantly impair its functionality.

Software Content Update: New or revised digital content added to an existing software application or platform, such as new features, functionality, or cybersecurity definitions.

System Redundancy: The duplication of critical components or functions of a system with the intention of increasing reliability.

Vulnerability: A weakness in an information system, system security procedures, internal controls, or implementation that could be exploited by a threat source.

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